

NOTES

Palladium(II) Pyridine Complexes Containing Trifluoro and Hexafluoroacetylacetonate as Counter Ions

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BIS(acetylacetonato)palladium(II)¹ and bis(ethylacetoacetato)palladium(II)² react with equimolar amount of a number of bases to transform one of the chelating ligands into the central carbon(C^β) bonded state. Whereas reaction of bis(acetylacetonato)palladium(II) with excess amines results in expelling the β-diketonate ligand from the coordination sphere either partly or fully giving rise to complexes having β-diketonate anions³. We have been studying the various linkage modes⁴⁻⁷ of β-diketones in palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes. As a part of this programme, reaction of bis(hexafluoroacetylacetonato)palladium(II) and bis(trifluoroacetylacetonato)palladium(II) with a number of nitrogen and phosphorus bases was studied. This communication reports the reaction of Pd(hfac)₂ and Pd(tfac)₂ with substituted pyridines resulting in complexes of the composition [PdL₂]X₂, where L is the heterocyclic base and X is the β-diketonate anion.

Experimental

Hexa- or trifluoroacetylacetonate was dissolved in equimolar amount of methanolic KOH and the solution slowly evaporated to dryness and then extracted with water. A solution of K₂PdCl₄ was reacted with the above ligands in 1 : 2 proportion and stirred for 1 h. The precipitate of Pd(hfac)₂ was filtered off, dried in vacuum and extracted with ether. Etherial extract was filtered out and the product crystallised by slow atmospheric evaporation. In case of Pd(tfac)₂, the dried precipitate was extracted with dichloromethane, filtered and the product was crystallised from the filtrate.

Pd(hfac)₂ (0.3 g) was stirred with γ-picoline 3 cc at 40° till it dissolved. The solution was kept in freeze overnight when light yellow crystals were obtained and recrystallised from dichloromethane-petroleum ether. The yield was almost quantitative (~90%). Pd(hfac)₂ and Pd(tfac)₂ were reacted with various bases in the similar manner and the products were obtained in 80-90% yield depending on the bases.

Analytical and physical measurements were done (Table 1) as reported earlier⁴.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compounds	M.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Λ _M Ω ⁻¹ cm ²
			C	H	N	
1.	[Pd(γ-pic) ₂](hfac) ₂	165	45.64	3.21	6.15	180
2.	[Pd(β-pic) ₂](hfac) ₂	163	45.58 (45.72)	3.18 (3.86)	6.12 (6.28)	192
3.	[Pd(α-pic) ₂](hfac) ₂	174	45.62	3.15	6.11	185
4.	[Pd(γ-pic) ₂](tfac) ₂	175	51.88	4.41	8.88	198
5.	[Pd(β-pic) ₂](tfac) ₂	170	51.85 (52.01)	4.45 (4.59)	8.85 (7.14)	200
6.	[Pd(α-pic) ₂](tfac) ₂	178	51.90	4.88	6.92	186
7.	[Pd(2,6-lut) ₂](hfac) ₂	156	47.95 (48.08)	3.82 (4.01)	5.71 (5.90)	188
8.	[Pd(2,6-lut) ₂](tfac) ₂	158	54.11 (54.26)	5.08 (5.24)	6.48 (6.66)	197

hfac = Anion of hexafluoroacetylacetonate,
tfac = Anion of trifluoroacetylacetonate.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of analysis, the complexes reveal the composition [PdL₂]X₂, where L is the nitrogen base and X is the β-diketonate anion. These are all yellow or light yellow crystalline solids soluble in acetone, chloroform and dichloromethane. In the infrared spectra of Pd(hfac)₂, three bands are observed at 1590, 1545, 1520 cm⁻¹ and in the case of Pd(tfac)₂, two bands at 1600 and 1530 cm⁻¹, due to C=O and C=C stretching modes. In case of [PdL₂](hfac)₂ type of complexes these bands are noticed at ~1680, 1630 and 1540 cm⁻¹, and in [PdL₂](tfac)₂ type of complexes at 1630, 1550 and 1510 cm⁻¹. Bands in the carbonyl stretching region almost coincide with those of the corresponding potassium β-diketonates. This indicates that the β-diketonates are not chelated, but are present as anions in the outer sphere. This has been further supported by the molar conductance data in acetone (Table 1) indicating 1 : 2 electrolytic nature. There are many absorption bands due to coordinated substituted pyridines. But the most characteristic band due to pyridine ring vibration appears in ~1610-1618 cm⁻¹ region. In the far infrared region ν_{Pd-N} is observed at ~330 cm⁻¹ region⁸ confirming the coordination of only the nitrogen atoms of the bases.

In the ¹H nmr spectra, methine proton signals of hfac anion appear above 5.9 ppm. Methine and methyl proton signals of tfac anion appear at ~5.6-5.8 and 2.2 ppm, respectively. Usually, methine proton of β-diketonate anion resonates in

higher field (low ppm scale) than chelated β -diketone. Hence, in conformity with earlier observations⁸, this confirms the presence of β -diketonate anions in the outer sphere. In addition to the above signal CH_2 and CH group proton signals of coordinated substituted pyridine, are observed at ~ 2.4 and $8-9$ ppm, respectively.

In solution, $[\text{PdL}_2](\text{ac.ac})_2$ type complexes usually dissociate to give $[\text{PdL}_2(\text{ac.ac})](\text{ac.ac})$ or $\text{Pd}(\text{ac.ac})(\text{C}^2\text{-ac.ac})^+$ type complexes. But $[\text{PdL}_2](\text{hfac})_2$ and $[\text{PdL}_2](\text{tfac})_2$ type complexes are stable in solution. Thus, in solution state, the relative stability of compounds containing β -diketonate anion in the outer sphere is in the order: $\text{ac.ac} < \text{tfac} < \text{hfac}$ ⁹, which is in accordance with the relative acid strength of the β -diketones¹⁰.

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Palladium(II) and Cobalt(III) Complexes of *p*-chloroisnitrosobenzoylacetone and *p*-bromoisnitrosobenzoylacetone

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p-CHLOROISNITROSOBENZOYLACETONE (*p*-Cl INBA) and *p*-bromoisnitrosobenzoylacetone (*p*-Br INBA) have been used as chromogenic reagents for palladium and ruthenium¹. However, structural investigations on the complexes of these ligands are lacking. In this communication we report the synthesis of solid complexes of palladium(II) and cobalt(III) with *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA and

their characterization on the basis of magnetic susceptibility measurements, ir, uv and pmr data.

Experimental

Physical measurements: Magnetic susceptibility of the complexes was measured by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the calibrant. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 221 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were taken on a Beckman DU-2 recording spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded using Varian spectrometer (100 MHz) with TMS as internal standard.

The molecular weights of the complexes were determined by cryoscopic method.

Syntheses of ligands: *p*-Cl INBA(I) and *p*-Br INBA(II) were synthesised by dropwise addition of sodium nitrite solution (4.6 g in minimum amount of water) to a solution of *p*-chloro- or *p*-bromobenzoylacetone (~ 10 g) dissolved in 30 ml of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was constantly stirred at $< 5^\circ$ and then poured into ice water when white crystals precipitate out. The crystals were collected, washed with water and recrystallised from methanol.

Syntheses of palladium and cobalt complexes of *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA: The palladium and cobalt complexes were prepared by reacting aqueous solution of metal chlorides with ethanolic solution of *p*-Cl INBA and *p*-Br INBA in 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratios, respectively, followed by dropwise addition of either sodium acetate (for Pd, pH 4) or sodium hydroxide (for Co, pH 6) solutions till the orange-red or yellow-orange complexes precipitate out. The precipitated compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Results and Discussion

The palladium and cobalt complexes were found to be soluble in chloroform, benzene, ethylacetate, methanol and acetone, and insoluble in water, carbontetrachloride and petroleum ether. The analytical results (Table 1) and the molecular weights of the palladium and cobalt complexes correspond to the composition of PdL_2 and CoL_2 , respectively. Similarly, the magnetic measurements have shown them to be diamagnetic. Therefore, palladium complexes must have planer structure whereas cobalt complexes should be octahedral. Cobalt(II) thus gets oxidized to cobalt(III) during complexation with isonitroso compounds.

Pmr spectra of palladium(II) and cobalt(III) complexes in CDCl_3 exhibit phenyl proton resonance signals in the range 2.2 to 2.6 τ and methyl signals in the range 7.35 to 7.5 τ . The proton signal due to NOH observed in the ligands (Table 1) at 1.84-1.86 τ , however, disappear in the complexes suggesting that the complexation leads to the replacement of the oxime proton by the metal ion.

The selected ir bands of the ligands and the complexes are given in Table 2. The OH stretching

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